

Bridging Awareness and Application: A Comparative Study of Generative AI Adoption, Training, and Ethical Perceptions among Research Scholars in Indian Universities

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In today's digital era there is a sharp rise in the application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) tools across various fields. The research scholars are also utilizing this technology in their academic activities. It has changed the traditional research methodologies used in academic works. However, several concerns related to plagiarism, presence of potential biases, and the maintenance of academic integrity have emerged. The purpose of this study is to compare the experiences and awareness of Ph.D. scholars of Mizoram and Tezpur Universities related to the usage of GenAI tools in their academic works. For this study, data was collected from 365 respondents with the help of semi-structured online questionnaires. The study tried to find the basic awareness levels, the institutional support systems, knowledge about ethical concerns, and the future perspectives of AI usage. For data collection, a snowball sampling method was adopted. All the necessary ethical safeguards and anonymity were maintained during data collection. The responses were analysed using SPSS. Several significant differences between the two institutions were identified in this study. The research scholars from Mizoram University are more active users and they also reported more benefits from AI tools. It was seen that institutional support and training opportunities were different between the two universities. This study suggests that in order to properly integrate AI technologies in higher educational institutes, there should be adequate training programs and clear institutional policies.

Keywords: Generative AI (GenAI), academic research, higher education, ai ethics, comparative study

In today's digital environment, Generative AI (GenAI) has transformed the process of academic research. These tools are used by researchers in several research methodologies. These tools can analyse large sets of data and generate research hypotheses in a very short span of time (Dowling & Li, 2025). These tools can benefit the research scholars to create new opportunities for research and thus increase their overall research productivity. However, if these tools are not utilised in an appropriate manner, then they can give rise to severe concerns, such as algorithmic bias, which can cause plagiarism, and transparency and accountability of research may be affected (Hanafi et al., 2025). According to Al-Zahrani (2023), students generally show a positive attitude towards GenAI in a higher education environment. But at the same time, they also highlight the need for appropriate training and ethical awareness regarding their usage in academia (Al-Zahrani, 2023). Nowadays, these AI tools can handle different types of data in their natural format. This allows researchers to analyse unstructured data with the

help of these tools (Dwivedi et al., 2023). Because of these advantages, these tools are adopted rapidly by the academicians, and therefore, the concerns about their misuse have also grown. Therefore, it is important for publishers, educators, stakeholders and authors to work together to promote ethical practices in academic writing (Lund et al., 2024).

Generative AI in Academic Research

In academic contexts, tools such as ChatGPT and DALL-E generate text, images, and synthetic data, supporting research activities such as idea development, literature review, and data analysis (Hanafi et al., 2025). These tools make the research process smoother and offer powerful analytical help, which speeds up scientific discoveries (Dowling & Li, 2025). GenAI helps to improve teaching and learning in colleges and universities by making education more personalised and helps the students build their skills. However, it can also make it harder for students to engage in critical thinking and develop independent problem-solving skills (Zhang, 2025). These tools used in academic research can create live images from scratch, write human like text, simplify complicated writing, check plagiarism and even put together brand-new datasets (Cotton et al., 2023; & Tzirides et al., 2023). These capabilities of AI tools can help scholars produce higher-quality content. To identify errors and improve their access to information. Such tools assist editors, authors, and publishers to disseminate scientific knowledge more efficiently and accurately (Abdul Razack et al., 2021).

Evolving Practices and Challenges in Academic Writing

Academic writing is a structured form of communication in which scholarly sources are synthesized to communicate a researcher's idea

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and engage in meaningful dialogue with the academic community (Noroozi, 2022). In academic writing, a well-organized discussion is required that contains clear section headings, rational summaries of research outcomes (Altmäe et al., 2023) and it should provide logical arguments with proper citations to prevent plagiarism (Liu et al., 2018). However, it can be seen that authors usually face difficulties related to limited subject knowledge, weak research capabilities and strict deadlines (Poch et al., 2020). They also face difficulties associated with different citation styles (Bautista & Pentang, 2022). GenAI tools are able to solve these problems to some extent. These tools have made it easy for the students and authors to refine their writing, generate summaries, and develop content more effectively. However, these tools can also create several concerns related to authorship, academic misconduct, and preservation of ethical standards. Therefore, it is very important for critical evaluation and responsible supervision of such tools in academic research and writing (Solak, 2024).

As AI technology is evolving rapidly, it is very important for higher educational institutes to adopt a balanced framework while adopting the tools and also ensuring their responsible use. This can be achieved by utilizing the potential of AI tools to transform education, but at the same time, the authors should also uphold academic integrity and address the emerging ethical concerns (Gupta & Nyamapfene, 2025; Zhang, 2025). One of the major concerns is that these tools may weaken the traditional research methodologies, as the existing tools for detecting AI-generated works are not fully reliable. Therefore, it is recommended that educational institutions should work more on students' critical thinking abilities and understanding of concepts (Shishavan, 2024).

The inappropriate use of these AI tools in academic research may not deliver reliable information. It has been found by some researchers that excess use of these tools could affect the critical thinking ability of the students. If these tools are not utilised wisely, then they may cause other problems, such as breaches of personal data and violations of copyright (Zhang, 2025). With the help of these tools, the classroom engagement can be enhanced, but at the same time, it is important for the stakeholders and students of educational institutions to adopt a careful strategy in their use (Gupta & Nyamapfene, 2025). In order to overcome these concerns, some of the universities have already created their own rules and regulations regarding the applications of GenAI tools in their institutions. According to guidelines of Newcastle University (2023), and the University of Queensland (2023), the students and teachers are provided with appropriate guidance and training to utilize these tools in an ethical manner. These kinds of approaches will enable the academic community to benefit from GenAI tools and simultaneously, it will also safeguard the integrity of their scholarly work.

Research Problem

It can be seen that there is an increase in the adoption of AI technologies across various universities globally. There is a limited understanding of how research scholars in Indian universities perceive and use these tools. The objective of this study is to fill this knowledge gap by comparing how research scholars of Tezpur and Mizoram University perceive and work with these AI tools in their academic activities. We wanted to see their awareness levels, the benefits they achieve, and what ethical concerns they might have. Through a side-by-side examination of the two institutions, this

study aims to offer meaningful insights into how AI integration influences academic standards, teaching practices, and administrative decision-making. This study will provide a foundation for developing guidelines and ethical frameworks that enable Indian universities to integrate AI tools into research activities in a responsible manner.

Objectives of the Study

To address the research problem, the present study formulates the following research objectives:

- To know the awareness, experience, and perceived impact of Gen AI tools among the research scholars of Mizoram and Tezpur University.
- To know the accessibility of Gen AI tools among the research scholars and to know how they assess their own level of competencies while using these tools.
- To know the levels of ethical considerations among the research scholars regarding the use of GenAI tools in research activities.

Method

Participants

This comparative study (Esser & Vliegthart, 2017) was conducted among research scholars from two Central Universities in India, Tezpur University and Mizoram University. Comparative studies are commonly used in educational research because they allow researchers to examine experiences and challenges across multiple institutional contexts, rather than within a single setting (Hantrais, 2009). A total of 365 research scholars participated in the study. Among them 186 were from Tezpur University and 179 were from Mizoram University.

Measures

In this study, we used a digital questionnaire for the collection of data. This is because online surveys offer several advantages compared to traditional paper-based surveys. This includes cost effectiveness, anonymity of respondents, and broader reach (Evans & Mathur, 2005). The study was composed of two sections: The first section focused on the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The second section was developed to explore the participants' viewpoints about various aspects of GenAI usage in academic research. For this purpose, a 5-point Likert scale (*strongly agree, 5 to strongly disagree, 1*) questionnaire was used in the study.

Procedure

The participants were selected by using a snowball sampling approach. The participants voluntarily completed the survey after being informed about the objectives of the study. Throughout the study, we made sure to follow strict ethical guidelines. Everyone who took part got a clear explanation of what the research was about and what would be involved. We also made sure that all answers remained anonymous and confidential.

Statistical Analysis

Once we collected the responses, the data was analysed using SPSS software. We calculated the mean and standard deviations of participants' agreement levels, based on which the results were analysed.

Results

Table 1

Demographic Characteristics

Demographic characteristics		N		%	
		TEZU	MZU	TEZU	MZU
Age	18-24	30	26	16.1	14.5
	25-34	123	116	66.1	64.8
	35 and above	33	37	17.7	20.6
	Total	186	179	100	100
Gender	Male	92	87	49.5	48.6
	Female	94	92	50.5	51.4

The demographic profile of the respondents from Tezpur University (TEZU) and Mizoram University (MZU) shows a balanced and representative sample across age and gender. A total of 186 participants from TEZU and 179 from MZU participated in this study. Majority of the respondents in both universities belonged to the 25-34 age group. The 18-24 age group accounted for (16.1%) of respondents in TEZU and (14.5%) in MZU, while the 35 and above category represented (17.7%) and (20.6%) respectively. Gender distribution was nearly equal in both institutions, with males (49.5%) in TEZU and (48.6%) in MZU, and females accounting for (50.5%) and (51.4%) respectively.

Table 2

Participants' Perspectives on GenAI, (TEZU AND MZU, 186+179=365)

	TEZU		MZU	
	M	SD	M	SD
Awareness and orientation towards GenAI				
1. I am aware of GenAI Tools	4.38	0.85	3.64	0.63
2. AI-generative tools have the potential to revolutionize academic research	3.69	0.95	3.44	0.54
3. GenAI tools can generate new insights and perspectives in research	3.60	0.75	3.58	0.68
Total Average	3.86	0.85	3.68	0.88
Perceived Impact on Research and Researchers				
4. GenAI tools enhance research productivity	3.46	0.85	3.84	0.69
5. GenAI tools improve research collaboration	3.55	1.10	3.55	0.67
6. GenAI tools reduce the time required for data analysis	3.72	1.00	3.94	0.61
Total Average	3.58	0.98	3.77	0.65
Usage and Experience with GenAI Tools				
7. Using GenAI tools has improved the efficiency of my research work	3.59	0.80	3.88	0.59
8. GenAI tools have expanded the scope of my research	3.19	0.92	3.83	0.63
9. I face no technical challenges while using GenAI tools	2.91	1.23	3.11	0.87
Total Average	3.23	0.98	3.60	0.69
Future Outlook and Recommendations				
10. GenAI tools will become more prevalent in academic and research in the future	3.67	1.32	3.86	0.83
11. GenAI tools have the potential to revolutionize the research landscape	3.40	1.09	3.79	0.62
12. Institutions should invest more in the development and integration of gen AI tools in research	3.85	0.88	3.53	0.82
13. Researchers should actively explore and embrace the use of GenAI tools in their work	3.86	0.92	3.55	0.66
Total Average	3.70	1.05	3.68	0.73

Awareness and Orientation towards GenAI (Table 2)

The respondents of TEZU show a higher level of awareness and orientation towards GenAI tools ($M = 3.86$) compared to the MZU respondents ($M = 3.68$). The most noticeable difference lies in the statement, "I am aware of GenAI tools", where TEZU respondents scored significantly higher (4.38 vs. 3.64). This suggests a greater familiarity among the TEZU respondents.

Perceived Impact on Research and Researchers (Table 2)

MZU respondents perceive a slightly stronger impact of GenAI tools on research productivity and efficiency, with a higher total mean (3.77 vs. 3.58). The respondents from MZU are in favour of the benefits of Gen AI tools. As it reduces the time for data analysis (MZU=3.94 vs. TEZU=3.72).

Usage and Experience with GenAI Tools (Table 2)

From Table 2, we can see that scholars from MZU have better experiences and more effective use of GenAI tools ($M = 3.60$) compared to TEZU ($M = 3.23$). The respondents from both universities have shown moderate levels of technical challenges.

Future Outlook and Recommendations (Table 2)

The respondents from both universities share similar opinions regarding the future of GenAI in academia (TEZU: 3.70; MZU: 3.68). Scholars from TEZU demonstrate stronger support for institutions to invest more in the development and integration of gen ai tools in research. The respondents from Mizoram University expressed greater optimism about the long-term potential and expanding role of generative AI in research.

Figure 1
Comparison of TEZU and MZU Responses

Note. Source: Author's own work

Table 3
Overall Comparative Summary

Dimension	Interpretation
Awareness and Orientation	TEZU respondents shows greater awareness and understanding of GenAI tools.
Perceived Impact	MZU scholars perceives greater positive impact on research productivity and time efficiency.
Usage and Experience	MZU scholars reports better practical experiences and fewer technical issues.
Future Outlook	Both groups are similarly optimistic about GenAI's role in academic research.

Table 4
Comparative Analysis on Training and Support

Training and support	TEZU		MZU	
	M	SD	M	SD
1. My academic institution provides adequate support for integrating GenAI tools in research	1.79	0.67	2.77	0.87
2. I have received proper guidance and training on how to effectively use Gen AI tools	3.69	1.14	2.45	0.68
3. My institution offers workshop on GenAI tools in research	3.86	0.68	2.45	0.86
4. I feel confident in my ability to use GenAI tools effectively	3.54	1.12	3.39	0.89
Total Average	3.22	0.90	2.76	0.83

Figure 2
Comparison of Training and Support for Gen AI

Note. Source: Author's own work

In Table 4 a difference is observed in item 1. Majority of the respondents from Tezpur University ($M = 1.79$) strongly disagreed that their institution provides adequate support for integrating GenAI tools, but MZU respondents agreed moderately ($M = 2.77$). This shows that there is a perceived gap in institutional support and training in both universities. Respondents at Mizoram University have benefited more from these training programs. From the table (item 4), it can be seen that respondents from both universities ($M=3.54$ & 3.39) perceive themselves as moderately competent in utilizing GenAI tools. The total average mean score of TEZU is 3.22 which is slightly higher than the mean score of MZU (2.76). This indicates that TEZU respondents reported a greater perceived level of access to training and support resources for the use of GenAI in research.

Figure 2 indicates that responses from Tezpur University display

slightly greater variability ($SD = 0.90$) than those from Mizoram University ($SD = 0.83$). This shows a wider difference in experiences and perceptions. Conversely, for the item related to institutional support, MZU exhibits higher variability ($SD = 0.87$) compared to TEZU ($SD = 0.67$). It is clear from the figure that TEZU reports the highest ($SD = 1.14$) for the item on receiving proper training, exposing their inconsistent experiences, whereas respondents from MZU show greater consistency ($SD = 0.68$). This indicates a uniformly perceived lack of training. Respondents from both universities show high variability regarding confidence in using these tools. The TEZU respondents have a higher SD compared to MZU respondents (1.12 vs. 0.89). This indicates that while TEZU may offer more opportunities, its accessibility is not uniform among the research scholars.

Table 5
: Comparative Analysis on Ethical Considerations

Training and support	TEZU		MZU	
Items	M	SD	M	SD
1. I am aware of the ethical guidelines and policies regarding the use of GenAI tools in research	3.71	0.88	3.14	0.88
2. I believe there should be transparency in the use of GenAI tools in research	4.01	0.72	3.80	0.77
3. Ethical considerations should be a primary concern when using GenAI tools in research	4.48	0.65	3.64	0.65
4. Researchers should actively discuss and address the potential biases of GenAI tools	4.34	0.70	3.78	0.67
Total Average	4.13	0.73	3.59	0.74

From Table 5, it can be seen that the respondents from TEZU have a higher level of ethical awareness. The total average mean score of TEZU is 4.13, compared to 3.59 of Mizoram University. The respondents of TEZU reported greater awareness of ethical guidelines ($M = 3.71$). But the respondents from MZU are less aware in this area ($M = 3.14$). This calls for improved training or workshops

on AI-related ethical guidelines at Mizoram University. The most highlighted difference appeared in perceptions of whether ethical considerations should be a primary concern when using GenAI tools. For item 3, the respondents from TEZU have a mean score of ($M=4.48$) and MZU ($M=3.64$)

Figure 3
Comparison of Ethical Considerations TEZU vs MZU

Note. Source: Author's own work

Analysis of Figure 3 reveals that, for Item 1, both TEZU and MZU report the highest SDs of 0.88. This shows that there is a broad spread of opinions within both groups. The reason behind this could be due to inconsistent exposures to institutional training initiatives. The average standard deviation is similar between the two groups (TEZU = 0.73, MZU = 0.74). This suggests that, although TEZU recorded higher average scores on ethical attitudes, the degree of internal agreement within each institution is nearly identical.

Discussion

The aim of this study is to examine and compare the awareness, usage, institutional support, and ethical considerations related to GenAI tools among research scholars at TEZU and MZU. The respondents from TEZU exhibited a higher overall awareness and orientation towards GenAI tools than their MZU counterparts. It may be noted that despite lower awareness, the respondents from MZU reported stronger perceptions of GenAI's practical impact on research productivity. This result is similar to what previous studies have found. Bankins et al. (2023) mentioned in their research that just because people use technology in their daily activities and see its benefits doesn't mean that they really understand how the technology works neither they are aware of all the features. In this study, researchers at MZU shared more positive experiences with GenAI tools. This result is similar to the findings of Perkins and Roe (2024). According to them, GenAI helps researchers handle large amounts of information, generate ideas, and support different types of research methodologies. The scholars from TEZU feel that formal support from their institution was lower, but they had chances to attend other workshops or training sessions. From this, we can conclude that even if Tezpur University offers fewer opportunities to the students, they find alternative ways to learn about these tools. On the other hand, MZU participants received more official support, but they had fewer opportunities to participate in those trainings. This shows that even if there are supportive policies in an institution, it does not mean that they are effectively implemented at the ground level. The authorities of Mizoram university should focus on this issue and they should adopt necessary steps so that the students feel easy to participate in the training sessions. This finding is similar to Jeilani and Abubakar (2025). The authors observed that although institutional support may facilitate students' access to AI tools, the real impact depends directly on the availability of hands-on training. One of the positive findings is that respondents from both universities showed agreement on the importance of ethical standards.

Conclusion

This research contributes to the growing body of literature on AI adoption in higher educational institutions. There are major dissimilarities across the two universities in the findings, which suggests that only knowing about AI does not automatically lead to using it. Universities should have proper support systems and infrastructures to make the implementation more effective. Based on the more effective. Based on the comparison of research scholars across the two universities, the study suggests practical, evidence-informed policy recommendations to support the responsible and effective use of generative AI tools. From our comparison of research scholars across the two universities, the study suggests practical, evidence-based policy recommendations to improve the ethical and effective use of Gen AI tools. In our study, we found that

some of the respondents were not able to work easily with GenAI tools. To fix this problem, the university could offer hands-on workshops and mentorship programs to reduce technical barriers. While most respondents recognize the benefits of these tools, academic communities should constantly work to overcome these challenges so that they can find the right balance between taking advantage of AI's strengths while avoiding potential problems.

This study has its own limitations. The sample was limited to two institutions, and the self-reported nature of responses could result in cognitive bias, which may lead individuals to overestimate their actual competence levels. Future research may be conducted by including institutions from different geographic regions and academic disciplines. They can also include qualitative methods such as interviews and focus group discussions, which could result in deeper insights into user motivations, institutional practices and other ethical concerns.

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